

**COVERAGE OF INDEPENDENCE ISSUES IN THE JOURNAL
“MILLIY TURKISTON”**

**Alijonova Gulnozaxon Muxammad qizi,
Associate Professor of the Department
of Social and Humanitarian Sciences
Oriental University**

In recent years, the formation of unions and alliances among states and nations has become something of a trend. Even when several states unite, they do so under various agreements and conditions, creating a union of states or a union of nations.

The European Union, planned for several decades, is now becoming a reality, forming a united structure of Europe's democratic states. Indonesia, which for one hundred and fifty years had been a colony of the Netherlands and consists of more than three thousand islands with a population of seventy million, has today achieved independence as a national state and, on equal terms with its former metropole—the dominant state—the Netherlands, has formed the Netherlands–Indonesia Union. Likewise, India, formerly a colony of France, has become an independent state and stands on equal footing with France, on the verge of establishing a Franco–Indian Union. India and Burma, long under British colonial rule, as well as the seventy million Muslims of Pakistan, having gained their national independence, now occupy independent positions within the Commonwealth in equal partnership with their former metropole, Britain. As a result, the oppression and discrimination of colonial peoples have ended, and the bloody struggles between colonies and metropolises have come to a close. Former colonial peoples, through their freedom and independent national states, have embarked upon the path of progress. The Jewish people, who for centuries had no national state, now possess their own national state named Israel, taking their place

among free nations and advancing along the path of national development, living freely.

The Bolsheviks claimed that outside the communist system, national independence and free unions of states were impossible, and that nations could live peacefully together only under the control of a communist state system.

Today, democratic states have clearly demonstrated—both in word and in practice—that the Bolsheviks’ accusations of “imperialism” were unfounded, and that their claims were false. As mentioned above, outside the communist system and despite the obstruction of the Soviet Union, Israel, Burma, Pakistan, India, Indonesia, and many other smaller nations have established independent national states and now live as equal and free nations. Many complex issues that could lead to war are being resolved peacefully through state alliances or through the United Nations (UN), and as a result, peace among these free states is being maintained.

The various forms of unions emerging today are based on the guarantee of national independence, the full realization of sovereign rights, and the principle of equality. Therefore, in such unions there is no place for colonial struggles between metropole and colony, nor for resistance against the hegemonic domination of one nation over others.

There exists, however, another form of union—the Soviet Union. From the day of its establishment, Soviet Russia forcibly occupied many nations and organized them under the name of a “union” as a union of republics. During and after the Second World War, Soviet Russia annexed numerous independent national states by force, reducing them to dependency and eliminating their independence and sovereignty in order to expand its own union. Thus, unionism has taken two completely opposite forms, and on this basis the world today is divided into two parts.

In one part of the world—the democratic world—new independent national states are continually emerging, and sovereign states are forming voluntary unions based on equality. Through this path, genuine freedom and peace are being

secured. In the other part of the world—the Union of Soviet Socialist Republics, that is, the Soviet Russian bloc—national independence and sovereignty are being eliminated. By suppressing the national rights, history, traditions, languages, and cultures of nations, the dominance of one nation is strengthened. As a result, the nations chained to the “union” of Soviet Russia, whose freedom is restricted, have never ceased their struggle to regain independence. In this part of the world, there is no peace, nor any factor capable of ensuring peace.

Despite the terrible terror of the Soviet regime, the continued struggles for freedom and independence by Ukraine, Turkestan, the Caucasus, and other non-Russian peoples are aimed not only at changing the communist system, but also at breaking free from the chains of Russian imperialism. The national liberation struggles of the people of Turkestan have a long history. In 1898, under the leadership of Dukchi Eshon, they rose against Russian imperialism. In 1916, there was a mass uprising. Between 1917 and 1923, bloody armed struggles were waged—all directed toward liberation from Russian imperialism and the attainment of national freedom. Today’s struggles are a continuation of those historical struggles; they are struggles for national independence.

The current national independence movements are even more resolute and determined than past movements, as they are directed against the Bolshevik system. It is now evident to everyone that the Soviet Union is not a free and equal union of nations or national states. The absence of even the slightest sign of sovereignty or national statehood among the nations chained to this “union,” and the baseless claims of voluntary unification, are clear to all. This union is a consolidation of Communist Party elites under Russian hegemony.

Therefore, it is essential to understand that the non-Russian peoples of the Soviet Union pursue two fundamental goals. First, to overthrow the Bolshevik totalitarian system; second—and most importantly—to struggle against all forms of Russian imperialism and to establish free, independent national states, living in

peace among other free nations. These two objectives are inseparable in their liberation struggle.

Unfortunately, views such as “national sovereignty obstructs global economic and political unions” or “national independence threatens world peace” are being propagated. Likewise, unjust claims that the United Nations or the Atlantic Charter do not apply to all nations are occasionally voiced. Although such theories may remain abstract and impractical, they provide material for Bolshevik demagoguery. While Bolshevik imperialism continues and intensifies the colonial policies of Tsarist Russia in an even more brutal form—oppressing small and weak nations in the most dishonorable manner—it nevertheless exploits the genuine thirst of oppressed peoples for freedom and sovereignty by presenting itself as a champion of national liberation, using such theories as propaganda against democratic states.

At home, Soviet Russia demands national nihilism from the oppressed non-Russian peoples—abandonment of national independence, traditions, and culture—while abroad it portrays itself as a defender of national independence. It employs every method to obstruct and undermine the work of the United Nations and seeks to construct a totalitarian “union of nations” under Kremlin domination.

The most dangerous enemies of national unity, freedom, and world peace are Soviet Russia and any imperialist ambitions that deny or suppress national independence. Without freedom, there can be no full peace. Without national independence, there is no freedom.

A nation deprived of its freedom and sovereign national state cannot participate as an equal member in any union of nations. In such circumstances, as in the Soviet Union, one nation dominates and violates the rights of others, leading to further unrest and conflict. Just and free unions among nations cannot arise without national independence. True democracy requires no distinction between the rights of large and small nations. The people of small and weak nations are not inferior; they too are entitled to freedom and happiness. Equality in relations

between large and small states can only be achieved on the basis of genuine democracy. Any racism or violation of national sovereignty reflects Soviet Russian imperialism and medieval barbarism and must be rejected by the democratic and civilized world.

The idea of national liberation and independence is growing stronger despite terror, violence, and prohibitions. Just as the rising of the sun cannot be stopped, this idea cannot be suppressed or destroyed by force. Let the enemies of independence not forget this truth!

To ensure lasting peace in the world, to establish full equality and freedom among peoples, to strike at all forms of totalitarianism and expansionist imperialism, and to create a free and equal union of nations, there is only one condition—national independence.

Therefore, let our slogan be: “Through National Independence to a Union of the World!”

REFERENCES

1. Buloqboshi. “Har narsadan avval milliy mustaqillik”// “Milliy Turkiston” jurnali. 1951-yil avgust-sentabr. № 74. - B. 15-18.
2. Behbudi, M. “The Language Issue.” In: *Selected Works* (Revised and Expanded 2nd ed.). Tashkent, 1999, p. 184.
3. Hoji Muin. “The Language Issue.” *Mehnatkashlar Tovushi* Newspaper, August 20, 1918.
4. Fitrat, A. “Unmatched Strings.” In: *Selected Works*, Vol. III: Dramas and Journalistic Articles. Edited by H. Boltaboyev. Tashkent, 2003, p. 232.

